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Heat carrier characterization for solar operation

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Authors

Name	Organisation	Email
Clarisse Lorreyte	DLR	clarisse.lorreyte@dlr.de
Juan Pablo Rincon Duarte	DLR	juan.rinconduarte@dlr.de
Martin Roeb	DLR	martin.roeb@dlr.de
Megan Kirschmeier	DLR	megan.kirschmeier@dlr.de

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Publishable executive summary

The PYSOLO (PYrolysis of biomass by concentrated SOLar pOwer) project brings together 9 partners from 4 EU countries with the aim of preparing the ground for a novel groundbreaking and fully renewable process combining concentrated solar power and biomass pyrolysis. Thanks to the use of solar heat in the pyrolysis process, the production of valuable products bio-oil, biochar and pyrogas can be maximized and the associated CO₂ emission minimized, with economic and environmental benefits compared to conventional pyrolysis. The proposed system uses particle heat carriers, ensuring operational flexibility and avoiding the need of heat transfer surface in the pyrolysis reactor that facilitates the system scale-up.

Specifically, PYSOLO process aims at developing at TRL4 the two key unit operations of this novel solar pyrolysis system, namely: (i) the solar particle receiver and (ii) the pyrolysis reactor with the associated particle-biochar separator.

The very innovative feature of PYSOLO lies in its innovative and unique coupling of pyrolysis technology with a high temperature CSP system. This ground-breaking feature can potentially offer the following main advantages:

- deliver solar bio-oil, electricity or pyrogas and biochar for many energy and non-energy uses, when solar energy is available;
- supply the heat necessary for the pyrolysis process, either in sunny hours or by exploiting high temperature stored solids;
- run the pyrolysis process in self-mode (i.e. with electric heating or by burning pyrogas and biochar), when solar energy is not sufficient and the TES unit is discharged;
- provide balancing services to the electric grid:
 1. by converting the pyrogas produced when solar energy or TES are sufficient to operate the pyrolysis process and the grid requires the generation of additional electric power;
 2. by using low-cost excess electricity from non-programmable RES (i.e. PV and wind) and converting it to high temperature thermal energy via the induction electric heating system.

In this deliverable, 6 different Particle Heat Carriers (PHC) are studied and compared using different approaches, including mechanical, thermal, optical and chemical properties, to determine a ranking between them. Among these 6 PHC, the 2 best candidates for the solar application are preliminarily selected for T3.3. This ranking is submitted to the other project partners involved in T2.2.2. The selection of the best PHC may change according to the application in the PYSOLO process, e.g. some PHC would be more suitable from the perspective of the pyrolysis reaction (RECORD and CSIC).

More information available at: <https://pysolo.eu/>

1. Introduction

In the PYSOLO project, the heat required by the pyrolysis reaction will be provided by a Particle Heat Carrier (PHC). The PHC is heated in a solar receiver at a temperature range between 600 and 800°C to enable a pyrolysis temperature between 400 and 600°C.

To determine which PHC would be the most suitable for the solar application in the PYSOLO process, 6 different PHC have been characterized and compared to obtain a final ranking.

This characterization considers mechanical, thermal, optical and chemical properties.

The ranking developed in this report is relevant for the WP3 and meets the specifications for the solar receiver but does not correspond to the final classification for the PYSOLO project.

The final ranking will be determined by combining the results of this deliverable with those of D2.2 and D2.4. Given that publication of these results is planned, and in view of the public nature of this deliverable, some confidential data is not detailed in this report but has been shared with the other members of the scientific consortium of PYSOLO.

Once this data has been officially published, it will be transmitted and uploaded in the EU portal.

2. Particle Heat Carrier characterization

In the following, the analysis of six PHC is presented. A first selection among different PHC was done in collaboration with other PYSOLO partners: POLIMI, CSIC, INERIS and RECORD. Six different PHC were selected for the characterization study. This choice has been detailed in D4.1.

Based on safety, costs, thermal and chemical parameters, the six PHC chosen for this characterization step were:

- Biochar (output product of the pyrolysis of the biomass)
- Bauxite
- Silicon Carbide (SiC)
- Magnesium Oxide (MgO)
- Olivine
- Sand

The size range of bauxite, SiC, MgO, olivine and sand is between 250 and 355 μm (Figure 1).

Figure 1. PYSOLO biomass and PHC studied for the characterization step (from left to right: wood chips, Biochar, Bauxite, SiC, MgO, Olivine and Sand).

In the next sections, the determination of several properties is described. At the end of this report, the final ranking of this study is presented to select the 2 PHC that are desired for testing in the solar receiver during the experimental campaign.

For each property, a system of points is utilized to compare the different PHC. 3 points represents the highest score and is given when the analysis for this property was excellent, 2 is given when the analysis gave a good result, 1 for a satisfactory result and 0 when the analysis did not give satisfying results.

Total points are tallied at the end to determine the final ranking.

2.1. Mechanical properties

For the heating of the PHC, a solar receiver will be designed, built and tested in T3.2 and T3.3.

The type of the receiver is a rotary kiln. To ensure smooth flow of the particles throughout the PHC system, including in the receiver and the two intermediate storage spaces, the flowability of the particles has been studied.

A first analysis concerns the flow of the particles along an inclined wall. To check if the heating of particles modifies their flowability, the measurements are performed at ambient temperature and after heating the PHC samples at 950°C.

A second analysis consists of the measurement of the angle of inclination of the particles (i.e., angle of repose). Indeed, according to many studies, this parameter can be a good indicator for the relative flowability of particles [1, 2].

Finally, the abrasiveness of the particles has been measured using a resonance acoustic mixer. Details of this method are described in the paper of Alkan et al. [3].

2.1.1. Wall friction test

To measure the flowability of the PHC on an inclined surface, 50g of each material is placed at one of the edges of a metal plate, first placed horizontally (Figure 2). The angle of inclination of the plate is slowly increased so the PHC gradually slides along the plate. A scale is placed at the opposite end of the plate to weigh the mass of the PHC, which is registered for each angle.

Each test was repeated 3 times at ambient temperature and 3 times for PHC samples previously heated to 950°C in an electric oven.

The cumulated mass collected at the bottom is recorded for each angle necessary to initiate flow. The angle at which the entire quantity of material falls, called the $\text{angle}_{\text{flow}}$, is measured for each PHC at room temperature and after heating to 950°C. The lower the $\text{angle}_{\text{flow}}$, the lower the wall friction, corresponding to better flowability.

The $\text{angle}_{\text{flow}}$ varies from 24° for the bauxite to 41° for the biochar.

Figure 2. Friction wall test with biochar.

2.1.2. Angle of repose

To measure the angle of repose, 50g of each PHC are poured through a funnel. The particles form a cone-shaped pile and the angle of repose is then measured by software analysis after processing a photo of the pile, as shown in Figure 3. Angles of repose are measured for the six PHC at ambient temperature. This

measurement is also performed on the non-flammable samples (bauxite, SiC, MgO, olivine and sand) that were heated in the electric oven (air atmosphere) to 950°C. The objective of these two measurements was to verify whether heating altered the mechanical behaviour of the PHC.

Figure 3. Example of picture used for the determination of the angle of repose.

The tests showed a difference of 1.9-7.7% between PHC at ambient temperature and PHC after heating at 950°C.

Sand, SiC and olivine yielded similar results: the average angle of repose ranged between 33 and 35°. The MgO has an angle of repose of 36°. The biochar has the highest angle of repose with a value of 45°. Finally, bauxite is the material with the lowest angle of repose with a value of 19°.

The angle of repose can be linked to the cohesiveness and relative flowability of granular materials.

As reproduced in the work of Shah *et al.* [4], according to the classification proposed by Carr, materials with an angle of repose below 30° have an excellent flowability, angle of repose ranged between 31 and 35° have a good flowability, between 36 and 40°, the flowability is fair and for an angle of repose above 45°, the flowability is poor.

Based on the angle of repose and wall friction tests, 3 points were attributed to bauxite since it shows the better flowability for both tests, 2 points for sand, SiC, and olivine which demonstrate good flowability and similar results, 1 point for MgO and 0 points for the biochar which reveals the least smooth flowability compared to the other PHC.

It should be noted that this result is probably related to the shape of the bauxite particles which are very round and regular compared to the other samples.

2.1.3. Abrasiveness

To estimate the abrasiveness of the different PHC, the different materials were placed in a plastic container closed at one end by a substrate. A resonance acoustic mixer (RAM, Resodyn, Butte, MT, USA) [3] was used to accelerate the PHC at 90G (about 883 m/s²) for 30 minutes. A comparison between the initial mass of the substrate and the mass obtained after the mixing test gives the abrasive property, similar to that found in a fluidized bed reactor. More details on this approach are described in [5].

Three types of substrates were tested: one made of steel 1.4841, one made of Inconel 2.4816 and one made of ceramic SIK-G. These three materials are potential candidates for the inner surface of the reactor. The objective of this study was to evaluate the potential abrasiveness between these samples and the different PHC. The results obtained with the steel and Inconel plates were very similar and demonstrated a low abrasiveness for each PHC. The most abrasive PHC was SiC but with an abrasiveness that remains acceptable. The tests done with the ceramic plate showed a more noticeable abrasiveness, specifically with SiC, MgO and bauxite.

We decided to attribute points based on results obtained with steel and Inconel since they are the most likely materials for the future reactor.

We attributed 3 points to every PHC except for SiC which demonstrated a higher abrasiveness but since this abrasiveness is still acceptable, we attributed 2 points for SiC.

2.2. Thermal properties

2.2.1. Thermal gravimetric analysis (TGA)

To verify the thermal stability of the different PHC, thermal gravimetric analyses (TGA) were conducted at 800°C in an inert atmosphere (N₂) and at 950°C under air flow conditions. The first tests at 800°C aim to reproduce experimental conditions in a pyrolysis reactor and the ones at 950°C the conditions in a solar receiver. The model used for these tests is the model STA 449 F1 Jupiter® NETZSCH Analyzing Testing. TGA tests enable the measurement of the mass variation of the sample during the heating phase and under isothermal conditions.

The results obtained are shown in Figure 4. TGA was not conducted with biochar to avoid clogging of condensable gases that could have damaged the device. The results showed that bauxite, SiC and sand remain stable even at high temperature (950°C). A mass loss of 4.5 % for the MgO and of less than 2 % for the Olivine at 950°C was observed.

Figure 4. TGA results for 5 PHC at 800°C (left) and 950°C (right) for 1 hour.

From this study we can conclude that every PHC except MgO remains very stable at high temperature. We could not test the biochar but we can also expect some mass loss at high temperature. Further analysis is ongoing to understand the reason for the mass loss of MgO (content of water, loss of ignition...). We attributed 3 points to bauxite, SiC, sand and olivine and 2 points for MgO, which is less stable at high temperature but still acceptable (less than 5% of mass loss).

2.2.2. Conductivity

Since several parameters have already been investigated experimentally, we decided to rely on values from literature for the conductivity and volumetric heat capacity. Once we have made our selection for the 2 PHC to be tested in the solar receiver, these properties will be investigated in detail for the chosen PHC.

The thermal conductivity of each PHC at 800°C has been compared using data from the literature (Table 1). It can be observed that MgO is the PHC with the highest thermal conductivity followed by SiC and olivine.

Table 1. Thermal conductivity of the different PHC.

PHC	Thermal conductivity [W/(m.K)] at 800°C	Source
Biochar	0.1-0.2	Literature [6–8]
MgO	0.8 – 1.2	Literature [9]
Bauxite	0.48	Literature [10]
Sand	0.41	Literature [10]
SiC	0.67	Literature [10]
Olivine	0.56	Literature [10]

Table 1 shows similar thermal conductivity for all PHC and higher one for MgO: for this reason, we have attributed 2 points to biochar, bauxite, sand, SiC and olivine and 3 points to MgO.

2.2.3. Volumetric heat capacity

The volumetric heat capacity of each PHC has been compared using data from suppliers and literature. As shown in Table 2, biochar is the PHC with the highest specific heat capacity. However, for optimal energy storage, apart from a high heat capacity, a high density is also required. Therefore, the best PHC with the highest volumetric heat capacity are bauxite, olivine and MgO.

Table 2. Ranking according to the volumetric heat density of the different PHC.

PHC	Specific heat capacity [kJ/(kg.K)] at 800°C	Density [g/cm ³]	Volumetric heat capacity [kJ/(m ³ .K)]
Biochar	1.35 [8, 10]	0.2 - 0.5	270-675
MgO	1.25 [11]	3.25	4062.5
Bauxite	1.05 [10]	3.5	3675
Sand	0.95 [10]	2.6	2470
SiC	1.05 [10]	3.2	3360
Olivine	1.25 [10]	3.3	4125

From Table 2, 2 points were attributed to bauxite, olivine, MgO, 1 point to Sand and SiC and 0 point to biochar.

2.3. Optical properties

To identify the best candidates from a solar point of view, accurate measurements of the optical properties of the PHC are required. The reflectance and transmittance of windows or coatings is usually measured with a spectrophotometer, and the absorptance can be easily deduced from these measurements. However, measuring the optical properties of particles is not a straightforward process. In recent years, Sutter et al. [12] have developed a method to measure these properties of a particle film, which has already been validated [13]. The reflectance of the six PHC was measured following the method described by Sutter et al. and this property is used to determine the absorptance and the thermal emittance to rank the PHC. Since the optical properties of PHC change during the different steps of the PYSOLO process, the following PHC samples were prepared and measured: 1) as received materials, 2) samples heated to 950°C in air (for the non-flammable PHC), and 3) samples after pyrolysis with biomass (wood chips).

2.3.1. Solar absorptance

The solar absorptance of the PHC was determined from the reflectance measurements made with a Perkin Elmer Lambda spectrophotometer in the range between 250 and 2500 nm, which covers most of the solar spectrum. The solid particles were placed inside a crucible which was closed using a glass window to retain the particles. The method used included the following steps:

- Measurement of the zero line of the device
- Measurement of the window transmittance and reflectance
- Measurement of the base line with a standard grey sample (reference)
- Measurement of window + reference

- Measurement of PHC in crucible + window

After computing the measurements, the solar reflectance as a function of the wavelength was obtained for each PHC. Using these data and the ASTM G173-03 standard (direct irradiance for air mass 1.5), the solar-weighted hemispherical reflectance was used to determine the solar weighted hemispherical particle absorptance. Detailed information of this procedure can be found in [12].

Table 3 shows the ranking obtained for the three groups of PHC samples; interesting results are observed:

- If the fresh samples are considered, absorptance vary between 0.48 and 0.99, and bauxite, biochar and SiC are the PHC with the highest solar absorptance.
- For the samples heated in air at 950°C (possible conditions for an open solar receiver), the solar absorptance of SiC and olivine increased, while for bauxite, MgO and sand it decreased. This effect can be explained by the colour change of the samples when exposed to high temperature (Figure 5b). Absorptance values vary between 0.35 and 0.99. For the reason explained earlier (flammable PHC), biochar was not studied for this analysis.
- When analysing the samples after pyrolysis, it was found that all PHC showed solar absorptance values above 0.9 and became good candidates for solar applications. This is due to the black colour that the PHC take on from the products of the pyrolysis process. (Figure 5c). Final absorptance values are ranged between 0.9 and 0.98.

Figure 5: Pictures of Olivine (a) as received, (b) after heating in air at 950°C, (c) after pyrolysis at 800°C

For the determination of the points: 3 points is attributed to every PHC with an absorptance between 0.8 and 1, 2 points for an absorptance ranged between 0.6 and 0.8, 1 point for an absorptance lower than 0.6.

Table 3. Ranking of PHC according to the solar absorptance (calculated in the range between 250 and 2500 nm).

PHC	As received [Number of points]	After heating in air at 950°C [Number of points]	After pyrolysis at 800°C [Number of points]
Bauxite	3	3	3

Biochar	3	-	-
SiC	3	3	3
Olivine	2	2	3
MgO	1	1	3
Sand	1	1	3

2.3.2. Thermal emittance (derived from reflectance measurement in the infrared range)

A good PHC must have high thermal emittance values to release the heat gained in the solar receiver to the biomass particles in the pyrolyzer. The thermal emittance can be derived from the measurements of the optical properties [14]. For the three groups of samples, reflectance measurements were also performed in the infrared range from 2.5 to 16 μm . The thermal emittance at 950°C was determined from these reflectance data and the procedure described in [12, 14].

Table 4 shows the classification of the three groups of PHC samples according to their thermal emittance. Bauxite, SiC and olivine are the best candidates when considering the samples as received and after heating in air at 950°C. Interestingly, MgO became the best PHC when the PHC after pyrolysis are considered.

An identical repartition to that for absorptance was applied for the distribution of points for the thermal transmittance results.

[4]

Table 4. Ranking of PHC according to the thermal emittance at 950°C.

PHC	As received [Number of points]	After heating in air at 950°C [Number of points]	After pyrolysis at 800°C [Number of points]
Bauxite	3	3	3
Biochar	3	-	-
SiC	3	3	3
Olivine	3	2	3
MgO	2	1	3
Sand	2	2	3

For the final score, the mean value between absorbance and transmittance values was calculated for each PHC to obtain a value between 0 and 3 (Table 6).

Although tests after heating in air and after pyrolysis could not be realized with char we still decided to attribute a grade of 3 to the char since pyrolysis and heating at high temperature should have no impact on either absorbance or transmittance values.

2.4. Chemical properties between PHC and material of the reactor

For this final analysis, we wanted to ensure that no chemical reaction occurred between the PHC and the material intended for the reactor's internal surface. Indeed, it is known that certain materials such as CaCO_3 can react with metal at high temperature and form hazardous compounds such as chromate [15].

For this study some samples of each PHC are heated in a furnace at 950°C (air atmosphere) for 1 hour on different substrates: steel, Inconel and ceramic SIK-G (Figure 6).

Only biochar could not be tested for this study due to combustion risk.

Figure 6. Picture of PHC samples on ceramic pieces (left) and picture of PHC samples on steel and Inconel pieces (right).

After this study, the steel substrates are analysed with SEM- EDX analysis to see if the chemical composition of the substrate surface has changed after being in contact with PHC at high temperature for 1 hour.

The results showed that contents of oxygen, chromium, manganese, iron and nickel are very similar to those of the steel samples received without any contact with PHC.

Analysis with ceramic substrate are still ongoing, but we do not expect any critical results since chromium formation mainly occurs with oxidation of steel.

This analysis does not show any critical PHC to be used with high temperature steel at the studied conditions. No points were attributed for this analysis since we could not do the test with the biochar and because none of the other PHC seems to have hazardous reaction with steel or ceramic

2.5. Other aspects to consider

Other parameters such as cost, safety and environmental aspects have to be considered for the final choice of the PHC. As an example, the price of the different PHC can vary significantly from one type to another, as it is shown in Table 5.

Other technical parameters can also influence the choice of the PHC to be tested in the solar receiver. If biochar is selected as a PHC to be tested, it means that the atmosphere in the solar receiver needs to be inert. Indeed, given that a temperature of 600 to 800°C in the solar receiver is targeted, the risk of combustion or gasification of the biochar is high if some steam or air enters into the reactor. The choice of biochar as PHC would introduce an additional constraint on the reactor design: the need for a completely tight reactor. Achieving 100% tightness in a solar rotary kiln is very challenging at high temperatures.

Table 5: Price of the different PHC

PHC	Price per ton (\$)	Source
Biochar	481-952	Literature [16]
MgO	1750-2000	Literature [[11, 17]
Bauxite	400	Literature [18]
Sand	150	Literature [18]
SiC	1900	Literature [18]
Olivine	175	Literature [18]

From Table 5, 3 points were attributed to sand and olivine, 2 points to bauxite and 1 point for MgO and SiC. Since in our case the char is one of our output products we will not buy it: for this reason, we attributed 3 points to the char for the price criteria.

3. Conclusion

This report presented the characterization of 6 different PHC in the aim of selecting the two PHC to be tested in the solar receiver.

The analyses were focused on mechanical, thermal, optical and chemical properties.

The final score for each PHC is found in Table 6.

Table 6 : Final score for each PHC

	Bauxite	Olivine	Sand	SiC	Biochar	MgO
Flowability	3	2	2	2	0	1
Abrasiveness	3	3	3	2	3	3
TGA	3	3	3	3	-	2
Conductivity	2	2	2	2	2	3
Volumetric heat capacity	2	2	1	1	0	2
Optical properties	3	2.5	2	3	3	1.8
Price	2	3	3	1	3	1
Others aspects					-1	
Total	18	17.5	16	14	10	13.8

Note that the biochar received a negative point for “other aspects” to account for the increase in complexity in the receiver design due to the need for a sealed system to avoid combustion.

It should also be noted that not all the analyses could be carried out for biochar (for several reasons mentioned in this report) and that the total points for biochar are therefore not completely representative.

From this final score, bauxite and olivine will be the 2 selected PHC to be tested in the solar receiver.

Nevertheless, this ranking is based on the requirements of the solar receiver. As mentioned in the section 2.5, others aspects must be considered and the final choice of the PHC for the PYSOLO project will be done with RE CORDE, CSIC, NOVA and INERIS partners based on results from D2.2 and D2.4.

The final ranking will be defined for the experimental test in the solar receiver (task T3.3), which is scheduled to start in December 2025.

List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
PHC	Particle Heat Carrier
TGA	Thermogravimetric Analysis
SiC	Silicon Carbide
MgO	Magnesium Oxide
SEM- EDX	Scanning Electron Microscopy- Energy Dispersive X-ray Analysis

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